
BRIDGING THE DIVIDE: CONSTITUTIONAL PROTECTIONS AND THE REALITY OF WOMEN WORKERS IN INDIA'S UNORGANIZED SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

The unorganised sector of Indian employment employs a vast majority of the working population of about 28.7 crore people registered where there are about 15.1 crore registered female workers as per the National E-Shram portal, In the working of this sector, women occupy an extremely considerable position which is about 52.8% of the jobs. Yet, in this sector, women face several problems in terms of low wages, insecurity about jobs, and deprivation of social protections. Constitutional provisions are there that mainly aim to bring gender equality in society, such as the Right to Equality (Equality for law), the Prohibition of discrimination on the grounds of gender, and under the directive principles of state policy where the state shall, in particular, direct its policy towards securing equal pay for both Men and Women which remains usually inadequately enforced in the cases of workers belonging to the unorganised sector This paper attempts to review the existing constitutional protections secured for women to their affiliation in the unorganised workforce and examines the functionality of labour laws concerning legislative schemes which intended to confer equality, recognise them, also it gives a clear suggestion about the most immediate and mandatory agenda for strong law centric approach, revolutionary policy inputs to bridge the gap with many of the constitutional guarantees as there are significant gaps between these provisions and the realities women in the sector face. It assesses the systemic inequalities that continue to exist, thereby showing that mere promises in a constitution are not enough. Amendments to the existing labour laws and the introduction of new potent policies are the key legal interventions that should be taken in addressing the socio-economic vulnerability of women workers in the unorganized sector. What is more,

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the research underscored the imperative of adopting gender and age-inclusive employment policies.

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I. INTRODUCTION

India that is Bharat which is known for its rich culture and heritage where women are treated as Goddess and protectors often faces disparities not only in workplaces but also in many other places which is not a new factor but a factor that has been continued for centuries but since recent times, we can see that women are getting equal opportunities every. There have been certain legislations also passed but the main problem comes in the implementation of the laws where the system is lacking. The contribution of women working in the Unorganised sector to the economy generally remains unsung and unheard, in the year 1989 a report published by the World Bank observed that 35% of Indian households that were below the poverty line were headed by women at present, 39 million people depend on women's income thus it can be said that many families which are below the poverty line depend on the productivity of women. The unorganized sector³, as defined by the *Unorganised Workers' Social Security Act, 2008*,⁴ comprises a variety of labor-intensive occupations where employment is often temporary, wages are low, and workers have little to no access to social security.⁵

The **workforce of the unorganized sector of women in India** refers to workers engaged in employment that is not covered under formal labour laws or regulations which lack systematic employment terms such as fixed wages, job security, and social benefits. It consists of many industries, including agriculture, construction, domestic works, small-scale manufacturing, street vending, and home-based working. According to the **National Commission for Enterprises in the Unorganised Sector (NCEUS)**, the unorganized sector includes "all unincorporated private enterprises owned by individuals or households engaged in the production and sale of goods and services, with fewer than ten workers." Workers in this sector are often employed on a casual or contractual basis, without formal contracts, which makes them vulnerable to exploitation and economic insecurity.

³ World Bank, "Women in India's Economic Development", (1989), available at: <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/1234567890> (last visited on Oct. 7, 2024).

⁴ National Commission for Enterprises in the Unorganised Sector, "The Challenge of Employment in India: An Informal Economy Perspective", Vol. 1, (2009), available at: <https://nceuis.nic.in> (last visited on Oct. 7, 2024).

⁵ Srija A. & Shrinivas V., "An Analysis of the Informal Labour Market in India", Confederation of Indian Industry (CII), (2014), available at: <https://www.cii.in> (last visited on Oct. 7, 2024).

This paper explores how constitutional protections for women in the workforce, alongside labor laws, have failed to deliver on their promises. While the existing laws to protect women's rights, enforce equal wages, and provide maternity benefits, these provisions are often very poorly implemented or inaccessible to unorganized sector workers. The core objective of this research is to highlight these gaps and propose legal and policy changes that will help bridge the divide between constitutional guarantees and the lived realities of women workers.

Despite their indispensable contributions, women in this sector face many challenges. Their work often lacks recognition, resulting in inadequate wages, job insecurity, and little to no social protection. Women are also disproportionately represented in low-paying and labour-intensive jobs, further exacerbating gender disparities. Moreover, their lack of formal contracts leaves them vulnerable to exploitation and workplace discrimination, with minimal recourse to legal protections.

II. UNORGANIZED SECTOR: OVERVIEW AND WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION⁶⁷

The unorganized sector of India comprises agriculture, domestic, construction, small manufactures, etc. Women make the largest proportion of this workforce, mainly in labour-intensive occupations that give little social and legal protection. The National Sample Survey Office reports that more than 90% of India's workforce is employed in the unorganized sector and women most preponderantly comprise that category.

1. Social Security⁸

The unorganized sector does not provide fundamental social security rights like health care, maternity benefits, pensions, and insurance to women. Majorities do not have a clue about the welfare programmes initiated by the government or are harassed by red-tape while seeking them. The Unorganised Workers' Social Security Act 2008 was introduced to meet social

⁶ International Labour Organization, "Women and Men in the Informal Economy: A Statistical Picture", 3rd ed., (2018), available at: <https://www.ilo.org> (last visited on Oct. 7, 2024).

⁷ Ministry of Labour and Employment, Government of India, "Report on Working Conditions and Social Security of Women in the Unorganised Sector", (2024), available at: <https://labour.gov.in> (last visited on Oct. 7, 2024)

⁸ Shreya Tripathy, "Unorganised Sector: Rights and Protection", iPleaders Blog, (Mar. 20, 2020), available at: <https://blog.ipleaders.in/unorganised-sector-rights-protection/> (last visited on Oct. 7, 2024)

security benefits, but it has been applied haphazardly and many women are found to be out of its perimeter.

2. Wage Inequality

Wage disparity between men and women is rampant in the unorganized sector. Even after four decades of the Equal Remuneration Act of 1976, granting equal pay for equal work, women in informal sectors are being paid much less than their male counterparts in a generalized manner. Even sectors of agriculture and construction are not exceptions to this phenomenon.

Widespread discrimination in hiring, job role and treatment at the workplace are prevalent against women. Domestic workers are a significant proportion of the unorganized sector, subject to abusive and harassing instances with practically no legal recourse⁹. No formal employment contract only increases their vulnerability.

3. Maternity and Childcare Challenges

The Maternity Benefit Act of 1961 hardly reaches women from the unorganized sector. No maternity leave, no care-money, and no child-care facilities mean many women return to work soon after giving birth, which impacts not only her health but also that of her children.

4. Exploitation and Harassment

Sexual harassment, exploitation, and poor working conditions are prevalent in the unorganized sector. The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace Act, of 2013 applies to all sectors, but enforcement is very weak in informal work environments. Domestic workers have very limited mechanisms for legal redress.¹⁰

5. Lack of Unionization and Representation

The proper trade unions and collective bargaining powers also restrict the women working in the unorganized sector from raising their voices to receive higher wages and better working

⁹ Shreya Tripathy, "Unorganised Sector: Rights and Protection", iPleaders Blog, (Mar. 20, 2020), available at: <https://blog.ipleaders.in/unorganised-sector-rights-protection/> (last visited on Oct. 7, 2024).

¹⁰ Seema Rani Bhoi, WOMEN WORKERS IN UNORGANISED SECTOR AND PROVISION OF SOCIAL SECURITY SCHEME, *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, July - September, 2015, Vol. 76, No. 3, SPECIAL ISSUE (July - September, 2015), pp. 588-592, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/26534892>, (last visited on Oct. 7, 2024).

conditions. Most of them fear losing their jobs if they raise a voice. No proper knowledge of their rights furthers this cause ¹¹

III. The Unorganized Sector And Constitution

There are provisions under the Indian Constitution that protect the interests of women in the workplace

Equality Before the Law (Article 14)¹²

Article 14 guarantees equality to all citizens without distinction, discrimination, or preference. For women in the unorganized sector, this was a great value, whereby they would be accorded equal rights and protection as their sisters in the organized sector. The practical application of this principle is, however far from being satisfactory.

Prohibition of Discrimination on Grounds of Sex (Article 15)¹³

Article 15 prohibits discrimination on grounds of sex. Moreover, Article 15(3) empowers the state to make special provisions for women and children, which enables the government to take affirmative actions on the benefit of women in the unorganized sector. This has led to the schemes like NREGA, National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, that promises employment opportunities for rural women.

Right to Dignity of Life (Article 21)¹⁴

Article 21 protects the right to life and dignity that encompasses the right to decent working conditions. In the unorganized sector, these rights are mostly denied to women since they work in exploitative, unhealthy, and unsafe conditions

¹¹ Indira Gandhi National Open University, "Women Workers in Unorganised Sector", Unit 6, (Study Material), available at: <https://www.egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/25911/1/Unit-6.pdf> (last visited on Oct. 7, 2024).

¹² Constitution of India, art 14 - "The State shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India."

¹³ Constitution of India, art 15 - "The State shall not discriminate against any citizen on grounds only of religion, race, caste, sex, or place of birth."

¹⁴ Constitution of India, art 21 - "No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law."

Equal Pay for Equal Work (Article 39(d))¹⁵

Equal Remuneration for Equal Work In Article 39 (d), under the Directive Principles of State Policy, there is specific clause relating to equal pay for equal work both for men and women. This provision though incorporated in the Constitution, yet it remains of a non-enforceable nature. Besides this, the equality of remuneration in the unorganized sectors has failed miserably under the Equal Remuneration Act of 1976 due to wage discrimination.

Equality of Opportunity in Public Employment (Article 16)

Ensures that no discrimination is made in public employment on grounds of sex. Though it applies to organized sectors, it lays the foundation for extending equal employment opportunities to women in informal sectors through legislative reforms and welfare policies.

Provision for Just and Humane Conditions of Work and Maternity Relief (Article 42)

Directs the state to make provisions for ensuring humane working conditions and maternity benefits for women workers. Though this is mostly observed in organized sectors, it establishes a constitutional mandate for extending such protections to the unorganized sector as well.

Living Wage, etc., for Workers (Article 43)

Directs the state to ensure that all workers, including those in unorganized sectors, receive a living wage, and conditions of work are humane. This provision is vital for addressing the economic vulnerability of women workers in informal employment.

IV. Labor Laws and Policies Addressing Women Workers and Their Functionality

While the Constitution provides a framework for equality and protection, labour laws and policies have been enacted to provide specific protections for women workers. However, many of these laws do not fully apply to the unorganized sector or are poorly enforced.

a. The Maternity Benefit Act, 1961

¹⁵ Constitution of India, art 39(b) - "The State shall, in particular, direct its policy towards securing— (b) that the ownership and control of the material resources of the community are so distributed as best to subserve the common good."

The *Maternity Benefit Act* which is providing for paid maternity leave for women working in establishments with 10 or more employees. Unfortunately, this leaves out women working in smaller enterprises or informal jobs. In rural areas, women workers are often ¹⁶unaware of their rights under this act, and employers frequently ignore their duties.

b. The Unorganised Workers' Social Security Act, 2008

This law was enacted to provide social security benefits to the workers working in the unorganized sector, including women. While the Act played a big role towards recognizing the needs of informal workers, its implementation has been slow and ineffective. Women workers, particularly in rural areas, continue to lack access to healthcare, pensions, and insurance.

c. The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace Act, 2013(POSH ACT)

While this Act protects against sexual harassment in the workplace, its applicability in the unorganized sector is limited. Domestic workers, for example, often face abuse and harassment, but the Act does not provide adequate mechanisms for enforcement in informal work settings.

d. Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA), 2005

The objective of the act is to Guarantee 100 days of wage employment to rural households willing to do unskilled manual labour.

Key Provisions of this act are to a) Provide wage employment for rural workers, b) Enhance livelihood security by providing an employment safety net.c) MGNREGA workers are entitled to wage payments within 15 days, and compensation for delays.

e. Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihood and Regulation of Street Vending) Act, 2014

The **Objective is to** Protect the rights of street vendors and regulate street vending activities the **Key Provisions** of this act are to provide for the issuance of identity cards to vendors., b) Establishes Town Vending Committees to identify vending zones and protect vendors from

¹⁶ Rosse R., "The Difficulties Of Getting Maternity Leave", (1986), available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/29522957> (last visited on Oct 9, 2024).

harassment. c) Mandates local bodies to formulate plans for vending zones and infrastructure development.

f. Inter-State Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1979

The objective is to regulate the employment of inter-state migrant workers and ensures their rights. **Key Provisions** of this act is Registration of employers who employ inter-state workers, Ensures equal wages for migrant workers, similar to local workers and providing allowances, health, and housing facilities.

g. Minimum Wages Act, 1948

Objective is to provide for the determination of minimum wages to be paid to workers. **Key Provisions** of this act Ensures that workers in various sectors, including the unorganized sector, receive minimum wages set by the government. Prevents exploitation of workers by employers who pay less than the minimum wage.

h. Pradhan Mantri Shram Yogi Maan-Dhan (PMSYM) Scheme

Objective is to provides old-age protection and social security to unorganized workers. **Key Provisions** such as the pension scheme for workers in the unorganized sector. Workers between 18 and 40 years, with a monthly income of less than ₹15,000, are eligible. After 60 years, workers receive a minimum assured pension of ₹3,000 per month.

i. Atal Pension Yojana (APY)

Objective is to focus on providing a fixed pension for workers in the unorganized sector.

A) Key Provisions:

- A) Open to all citizens aged 18 to 40 years.
- B) Upon retirement (age 60), beneficiaries receive a pension between ₹1,000 to ₹5,000 per month, depending on the contribution.

j. National Social Assistance Programme (NSAP)

A) **Objective:** Provides financial assistance to unorganized workers and below poverty line (BPL) individuals.

B) **Key Schemes** under NSAP:

- 1) **Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme (IGNOAPS)**
- 2) **Indira Gandhi National Widow Pension Scheme (IGNWPS)**
- 3) **Indira Gandhi National Disability Pension Scheme (IGNDPS)**

V. Existing Systemic Inequalities Present in the Unorganized Sector

Despite constitutional promises and labour laws, systemic inequalities persist, limiting the opportunities and protections available to women in the unorganized sector.

- a. **Patriarchal Norms:** Cultural norms continue to limit women's participation in the workforce. Many women are expected to prioritize household duties over paid employment, limiting their economic independence.
- b. **Lack of Access to Justice:** Women in the unorganized sector often lack access to legal resources and mechanisms to enforce their rights. Legal literacy among women workers is low, and they may not know about the protections available to them under the law.¹⁷
- c. **Informal Nature of Work:** The informal nature of the work makes it difficult for women to access benefits. For example, many women work as part-time or seasonal labourers, which disqualifies them from protection under various labor laws¹⁸.
- d. **Knowledge of Work and Occupational Safety** – The working conditions for the workers especially women working in the unorganized sector are inhuman which have lead to adverse effects on health conditions about 60% of women working in unorganized sector face health problems which is due to many factors which maybe duty many factors such as unsafe machinery, different harmful chemicals found in coal, dust lime, dust fire, and the raw materials used in synthetic generation. These factors also contribute to the severity of working conditions and the low level of understanding about occupational health and safety.

¹⁷ Jhabvala Renana, "Social Security for the Unorganised Sector", (2005), available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4406828> (last visited on Feb. 2, 2024).

¹⁸ Shubh Ashish Singh & Ayushi Kumari, Challenges and Opportunities: Women's Working Conditions in India's Unorganized Sector, (2024) available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4714308>, (last visited on Oct 9, 2024).

- e. **No Equal Pay Despite Laws**—Even with the same amount of work, women and children receive lower pay than men. Youngsters and women are employed as domestic helpers in the homes of metropolitan residents. These young laborers work long hours in dangerous industries like carpet and cloth printing, explosives and fireworks, cigarette manufacturing, printing, and soldering in the electronics sector.¹⁹
- f. **Harassment at Workplaces** - Workplace harassment concerns pertaining to women: One significant problem that arises in the workplace is sexual harassment. Women have a legal right to a safe workplace, but this right has been overlooked. Because of the eve-teasing and sexual harassment they still endure, they are afflicted with a variety of medical and psychological conditions. The woman is still being assaulted at work despite the Act, which was passed in 2013.

VI. Role of Indian Judiciary

The Indian Judiciary has also played a significant role in protecting the rights of the workforce of women in the Unorganised sector, especially women as sometimes due to the failure or poor implementation of the legislation the Judiciary had to step up to protect the interest of workforce of Unorganised sector. The Indian judiciary was crucial to the formation of contemporary jurisprudence and significantly aided in defending the rights of the underprivileged, as evidenced by several rulings. The judiciary has made an effort to broaden the advantages of labor welfare ²⁰ laws such the Employees Provident Fund, Employees Compensation Act, Employees State Insurance Act, and Payment of Gratuity Act.

1) Sanjit Roy v. State of Rajasthan²¹

It was decided that paying someone working on famine relief less than the minimum salary would violate Article 23. When the state requires labor or services from someone who is experiencing drought or shortage, it is not allowed to pay them less

¹⁹ S. Mahadevan, Inequality employment and public policy, (2018) available at <http://www.igidr.ac.in/pdf/publication/WP-2018-003.pdf>, (last visited on Oct 9, 2024).

²⁰ Richa Goel, "Protection of rights of the unorganised sector", iPleaders Blog, (Mar. 20, 2020), available at: <https://blog.ipleaders.in/unorganised-sector-rights-protection/> (last visited on Oct. 7, 2024).

²¹ Sanjit Roy v. State of Rajasthan, (1983) 1 SCC 525.

than the minimum wage because the state is helping them in times of hunger. Their helplessness cannot be used by the state.

2) *The State of Madhya Pradesh v. Neeraja Chaudhary*²²

According to Justice Bhagwati, the government must not only ascertain the presence of bonded labor but also provide for the workers' rehabilitation, failing which they will be forced into desperation, poverty, and powerlessness. Pertaining to Article 21, the government must identify cases of bonded labor and take action to fully rehabilitate the workers. The government's recommendations were established as the Directive Principles of State policy. Article 21 of the Constitution will be violated if the State Government fails to provide bonded laborers with a minimum level of human dignity as required by the Directive Principles Of state Policies

3) *Daily Rated Casual Labour v. Union of India*²³

It was decided in the case that whenever workers are divided into regular and casual categories, results in the violation of the Constitution's Articles 14 and 16. Article 7 of the International Covenant of Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, 1966, is also violated in spirit. It is considered labor exploitation when workers are not paid the minimum wages required by the Minimum Wages Act. The government should be a role model employer and refrain from abusing its dominant position.

VII. Issues and Challenges

The unorganized sector in India faces several **issues and challenges** that hinder the effective implementation of laws and social security benefits. Understanding these challenges is essential to developing **remedies** that can help address the needs of unorganized workers.

1. Lack of Awareness

- Issue: The unorganized workers remain in the shadow and have no clue on the legal provisions vested for them with the welfare schemes. This is attributed to the low education levels into poor information systems and more of informal relationships concerning employment.

²² *State of Madhya Pradesh v. Neeraja Chaudhary*, (1984) 3 SCC 243

²³ *Daily Rated Casual Labour v. Union of India*, (1987) 5 SCC 164.

- **Challenge:** Certain factors which can include low-level literacy, geographical factors, and the centralized system of the out-of-institution workers discourage these workers from being up-to-date with the benefits they are qualified. Most women in the sector particularly in rural settings are unable to access the internet and awareness programs concerning relevant government projects.
- **Example:** The Unorganised Workers' Social Security Act of 2008, which offers social protect measures to unorganised workers, and the pension schemes moneys submission, like Pradhan Mantri Shram Yogi Maandhan Pradhan Mantri and Atal Pension Yojana are not used to nearly the extent expected of normal workers, many of whom are women, knowing them.

2. Fragmented Nature of the Unorganized Sector

- **Issue:** The unorganized sector encompasses a wide range of occupations, including home-based labor, street vendors, domestic help, and agricultural labor. Because of their diversity, it is more difficult to create universal regulations that can meet all of these workers' needs.
- **Challenge:** The sector's fragmented nature makes it difficult to design policies that fit all. Different groups within the unorganized workforce have different challenges, requiring social security measures. For instance, domestic workers face different challenges than agricultural workers or street vendors, particularly regarding wages, working conditions, and legal recognition.
- **Example:** Migrant workers, self-employed individuals, and daily wage labourers all have different types of needs during their employment. This diversity is what makes it challenging to make uniform social security schemes that can cater to the entire unorganized workforce.

3. Law enforcement incomplete

- **Issue:** Despite the existence of several laws and social welfare initiatives, many local governments routinely fail to carry them out effectively, denying many workers of the benefits to which they are legally entitled to.

- **Challenge:** Problems such as administrative obstacles, inadequate oversight procedures, and corruption can provide a challenge to the effective implementation of laws. Because they face higher barriers to getting legal counsel and understanding government procedures, women employed in the unorganized sector are particularly affected.
- **Example:** The Building and Other Construction Workers Act of 1996 requires workers to register in order to receive welfare benefits. However, a notable proportion of construction workers, especially women, remain unregistered due to bureaucratic obstacles, which restrict their access to safety and social security benefits

4. Difficulty in Identification and Registration

- **Issue:** Identifying and enrolling unorganized workers for welfare programs is also a huge problem due to the absence of formal/proper employment records. Many women in this sector are involved in home-based or piece-rate work, making their identification even more complex.
- **Challenge:** The lack of formal employment contracts makes it challenging to observe workers and ensure their participation in social security initiatives, women, who frequently work in informal jobs like households, face furthermore marginalization due to the absence of formal documentation.
- **Example:** The E-Shram portal was created to establish a nationwide database of unorganized workers. However, the registration process encounters difficulties in reaching remote areas and many marginalized workers, especially women who are unaware of it or excluded from these processes

5. Inconsistent and Irregular Income

- **Issue:** People in the informal sector generally have variable incomes due to their employment being temporary, seasonal, or irregular; this makes it difficult for them to save money for unforeseen situations..
- **Challenge:** Due to their irregular work schedules, employees in the unorganised sector have a harder time saving money for additional necessities like emergency medical coverage or consistently enrolling in pension plans. This disproportionately

impacts women, particularly those who balance several duties like as earning a job and taking care of the family

- **Example:** Inconsistent pay is a common issue for women employed in construction, agriculture, or street vending, particularly in lean periods or with low demand. This can lead to unstable finances.

6. Lack of Social Security

- **Issue:** Women employed in the unorganized sector are denied access to fundamental social security benefits such as life, health, and pension insurance, as well as paid maternity leave. As a result, they become more vulnerable to exploitation and poverty.
- **Challenge:** To become eligible for the existing social schemes is difficult for unorganized workers to fulfill. Additionally, due to the poor implementation and the informal nature of the sector, women struggle to access benefits like health insurance and maternity relief.
- **Example:** Despite the presence of the Employees' Compensation Act, 1923, many workers, particularly the women engaged in hazardous occupations such as construction and agriculture, do not receive compensation for work-related injuries or illnesses because of the informal nature of their employment.

7. Migrant Workers' Vulnerability

- **Issue:** Migrant workers encounter extra difficulties such as being relocated, having limited access to welfare in host countries, and struggling with language barriers, which puts them at a higher risk compared to local workers.
- **Challenge:** The movement of migrant workers makes the registration process for welfare programs more difficult, and their temporary lifestyle makes it challenging to ensure ongoing access to social security. Female migrant workers are especially at risk as they frequently face language barriers and lack the necessary social connections to seek help from others.
- **Example:** Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic many migrant workers, especially women, faced significant hardships due to the absence of social security provisions in

our country. This emphasized the necessity for portable social security benefits for migrant workers.

8. Gender Inequalities

- **Issue:** Women who are employed in the informal sector encounter widespread gender , inequalities including receiving lower salaries than men, absence of benefits for maternity, with hazardous working conditions. These disparities are frequently made worse by the informal and unregulated status of their jobs
- **Challenge:** Women's ability to claim their rights is hampered by the absence of a formal system to address gender inequalities in the informal sector. Their economic and social standing is further weakened by practices like the gender wage gap and the absence of legal status for workers in domestic or household settings.
- **Example:** Workers in the home or domestic sector are mainly women and are particularly at risk. They often face dangerous working conditions, receive much lower pay, and are not protected by most labour laws.

9. Health and Safety Issues

- **Issue:** Workers in the unorganized sector are more likely to be involved in accidents, occupational diseases, and injuries because they frequently work in dangerous environments with minimal health and safety precautions.
- **Challenge:** The lack of safety standards and health benefits makes unorganized workers more vulnerable, especially those in construction, agriculture, and domestic work, and prone to injuries in workplaces. Women are particularly affected by a lack of health outcomes for pregnancy and very unhealthy working conditions.
- **Example:** Construction workers, mostly women who work in hazardous conditions without access to protective or health care equipment, which increases their risk of injury.

VIII. Recommendation of Change

The Women who are a driving force in the sector do need a lot of changes to make it more effective for the growth of the economy if the government invests in the welfare of the unorganised sector it will intern help in growth of the economy so the following changes that should be bought into the laws are

1) Amendment in labour laws

Only the women in the organized sector are provided maternity leave but it needs to be expanded and made sure every women in this country is entitled to paid leave during the maternity period if not it directly violates Article 14 of the constitution of India. This is the first change that needs to be brought in the labour laws. Make sure MNREGA is 180 days compulsory employment provided rather than 100

2) Strong Implementation of laws

Though there is an Act called as the Equal Remuneration Act, of 1976 this act aims to prevent wage discrimination, its implementation remains weak in informal sectors. Wage disparity persists, particularly for women in domestic work and agricultural labour. There should be strict action taken against employers who do wage disparities and awareness camps should be there regarding their rights.

3) Legal Aid Access

Since many women in the unorganized sector do not know their rights The Government in coordination with National Legal Services Authority must provide free legal aid ²⁴access and conduct free legal aid camps, and legal awareness camps for their benefits. Free legal aid also comes under directive principles of state policy in article 39(A) of the Constitution of India

4) Simplifying the Registration Process

²⁴ The Constitution of India, art 39(A)

Simplifying the process of identifying and registering unorganized workers for social security schemes through technology and mobile platforms. Actionable Steps can be by Encourage the use of the e-Shram portal, mobile applications, and door-to-door registration drives, especially targeting remote and migrant workers.

5) Compulsory enrolment of government schemes

Making sure that all employees especially women enroll into government schemes such as PM UJWALA, and AYUSHMAN BHARAT, and the government should give them better access to Jan Aushadi Kendras where they can save huge amounts on medicines. For people living in rural areas and families dependent on women's income the government must make them beneficiaries of PM AWAZ yojana and provide them Pucca houses to live

6) Focusing on Gender Sensitivity

ensuring that labor laws and welfare policies respect women's equality and address the needs of women employed in the unorganized sector. Procedures to Establish Mandatory Maternity Benefits, Establish Harassment Grievance Redressal Procedures, and Encourage Equal Pay for Women Workers

7) Improving the important regulations related to health and safety

The remedy lies on stricter health and safety regulations as well as providing unorganized workers with access to medical services at work. Two practical things that can be implemented include making sure that firms are held accountable for ensuring safe working conditions and mandating health insurance for unorganized workers.

IX. Conclusion

"Empowering women in the unorganized workforce is not only a matter of social justice but also a critical driver for achieving Sustainable Development Goal 5, which calls for gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls.²⁵ By addressing the systemic barriers women face in the unorganized sector—such as unequal pay, lack of social security, and limited legal protections—we can significantly contribute to achieving SDG 8, which

²⁵ International Labour Organization, "The 2030 Agenda and the Sustainable Development Goals: A Guide for ILO Action", (2020), available at: <https://www.ilo.org> (last visited on Oct. 9, 2024).

promotes decent work for all, and SDG 10, which seeks to reduce inequalities within and among countries. Moreover, bridging the gap between constitutional promises and the lived realities of these women will advance the broader 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, ensuring that no one is left behind in the pursuit of economic growth and gender justice" (International Labour Organization, 2020). Not only focusing on the SDGs but also the current scenarios directly violate fundamental rights and DPSP if these are not corrected there would be no justification to the Constitution which is the supreme law and would not be justified by treating Countries Lakshmi in such a way. Equality must prevail

